

ISic2949

I.Sicily inscription 2949

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

found during construction work between via Eumelo, via Archia, and via Carabelli

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644858

Bibliography

Gentili, G.V. 1961. Nuovi elementi di epigrafia siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 7: 5-25. At 20 no.2 dr

Manganaro, G. 1963. Nuove ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 16: 51-64. At 62-63 ph

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2949. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387781>